

An Overview of Online Marketing: It's Present and Future Prospect – A Study in Northern Region of Bangladesh

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Abstract:

The objective of this research is to provide an inside scenario about the internet marketing in Bangladesh. Basically this study investigated the impact of prior purchase experience of customer, product quality, price, availability, distribution system and promotional programs on future purchase intention. Primary data were collected by using Dichotomous scale from the northern region of Bangladesh and the sample size was 150. In the present era, every business organization is using internet for conduction business activities. The Internet has become an indispensable tool for today's businesses. Bangladesh has also stepped into the arena of e-commerce slowly but surely. Our study found that quality products, attractive promotional activities, efficient distribution channel, awareness about online marketing and product availability positively influenced purchase intention but prior online purchase experience, perceived social benefits and price can't influence purchase intention in online shopping context. Our study will help the marketer for knowing the factors regarding the purchase intention of customers. The study was limited to the attitudes and perceptions of the selected sample respondents and may not be universally applicable. There was a possibility of the respondent bias in self-reporting perceptions of the survey. Prior research can't describe the impact of prior purchase experience of customer, product quality, price, availability, distribution system and promotional programs on future purchase intention of customer. Upon the study results some necessary recommendations has been given in this study.

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INTRODUCTION

Internet marketing (IM) is also known as digital marketing, web marketing, online marketing, or e-marketing. As the name states, it is the advertising of products or services over the Internet. However, it also implies marketing through the wireless media and through e-mail. Electronic customer relationship management (ECRM) systems are also categorized under Internet marketing. IM can be creative, as well as, technical through its design, development, advertising, and sales over the Internet. In today's world of information not only as one of the main resources and assets are recognized organizations but also by literature and other resources and tools for effective management of assets (Financial resources, manpower, etc.) is also of importance and thus has special value. But this value will be achievable only if the researcher and their data at the right time, with quality and safety acceptable to the appropriate people and adhered to the optimal organization is established. Hence it is that the underlying information technology, transport, handling, use and management of effective information believers in the drawer is released, has been of crucial importance. Therefore, in line with Iran's twenty-year vision of a developed society with regard to the impact of ICT on various aspects of human life and it is especially crucial and sensitive aspects of cultural, economic, security, social, commercial and political, Ministry of Communications and Information Technology on the overall development action plan designed to offer comprehensive IT plan to the country in 2003. The agreement includes five major projects, development of large IT projects, program executive tasks in the field of security (AFTA), create the database status information technology, information technology applications in developing countries and provide the framework and drafting bills and legal regulations and preparing compute crimes and E-commerce laws. One application of information technology is E-commerce and E-commerce is "a general concept covering any form of business transactions or information exchange executed using information and communication technology, between companies, between companies and their customers, or between companies and public administrations. Electronic Commerce includes electronic trading of goods, services and electronic material. E-mail marketing is one of the subsets of the following: E-mail marketing is a form of direct marketing which uses E-mail as a means of communicating commercial or fund-raising messages to an audience. In its broadest sense, every E-mail sent to a potential or current customer could be considered E-mail marketing. However, the term is usually used to refer to sending E-mail messages with the purpose of enhancing the relationship of a merchant with its current or previous customers, to encourage customer loyalty and repeat business, sending E-mail messages with the purpose of acquiring new customers or convincing current customers to purchase something immediately and adding advertisements to E-mail messages sent by other companies to their customers. Researchers intend in this article regarding the important role of E-commerce in IT development in Iran to introduce advantages and disadvantages of E-mail marketing and also to introduce strategies that increase the efficiency of this tool will pay.

The introduction and transmission of the Internet phenomenon into the business arena guiding the marketing discipline to various changes and strong challenges. Since the revolution of online based market marketing practice has been busy with integrating the potential of information and communication technologies through the utilization of databases and online marketing. Billions of potential consumers can now be reached this way. In recent times, online marketing has secured its place as the preferred marketing method. For an industry that emerged only within the past decade or so, online marketing has gained popularity quickly. It is now attracts a greater portion advertising dollar than any other

media type, including TV, Radio, Print and others. For business to stay ahead, or perhaps even stay in the game, marketers need to have an effective online marketing strategy. Online marketing provides a new force of attracting more quality sales leads, increasing business revenue, enhancing business profitability, improving business sustainability in the competitive global market. Online marketing also referred to as i-marketing, web marketing, Internet marketing, or e-marketing, is the use of the Internet to advertise and sell products and services. Within the definition of Online Marketing people will find mention of pay per click advertising, banner ads, e-mail marketing, search engine marketing (including search engine optimization), blog marketing, and article marketing. Each of these subject areas is important to consider prior to planning suitable internet marketing strategy. A website and online presence is one aspect of the marketing mix for a business. For the small to medium business, there is no reason for a website to be the sole method of marketing – but by integrating a website into marketing plan organization can drive new leads and generate new business that wouldn't ordinarily reach using a single avenue of advertising. To outline e-promotion includes: Banner promotion, Web public relations (WPR), E-leaflets and having a domain name. The e-marketing mix must work together and support each other if the company is to have a successful online marketing strategy. So just as when marketing in the offline world, keeping online marketing mix balanced using a combination of immediate traffic generation, midterm strategies and long-term targeted traffic magnets. With a good balance marketers can have a good launch, and then continue to see sales from that product, service or affiliate marketing promotion for some time to come as turn focus to next money-making opportunity. So e-commerce has grown by leaps and bounds and continues to set new marks every year. Online marketing is attractive because it levels the playing field for all competitors, big and small. Dominant brick and mortar companies use marketing firms to push their brands on television, billboards, magazines, and so on. When the companies open a site, they often have these marketing firms handle their internet efforts as well. Crushing them on search engines is like taking candy from a baby. They haven't a clue what they are doing, but their superiority will never let them acknowledge they are paying triple the going rate for advertisements on high traffic sites. Unlike 'click only' and 'brick and mortar' and 'click and mortar' cover marketing effort both in conventional and online arenas. Since the inter connection with information with information super highway click and mortar becomes the crucial path to be flourished for a conventional business entity. Even before the Internet there were many different ways to advertise, in different media such as radio, TV, newspapers, magazines, as well as via telemarketing or pamphlets. Usually the goal was to get a company- and/or product name, a statement etc. communicated to as many people as possible for the smallest price possible. When the Internet arose, a number of search options became available. Companies had the option to advertise themselves on a larger scale. Due to advertising perception at the time, many businesses were assumed to have great value, and thus traded on the stock exchange at extraordinary high rates. This collapsed in 2001 at what is commonly known as the dot-com bubble. After the dotcom collapse, the Internet was almost disregarded because of many failing website-based businesses that had expectations to the market and assumptions about consumers. However, both consumers and companies continued exploring online options. Soon more substantial business models emerged; search advertising¹ and e-commerce were the new possibilities. Enhancements in targeting advertising, and understanding how websites maintain visitors, became relevant. Researching consumer's behavior and buying patterns online began to interest scholars. There are over 2 billion internet users Worldwide in 2011 and it is forecast this number will exceed 3 billion by 2015 and the world B2C e-commerce industry generated between \$400

billion and \$600 billion in 2010 according to yStats.com, which estimates the market will generate somewhere from \$700 billion and \$950 billion in 2015. Social media continues to fuel the B2B e-commerce market, which aims to boost electronic business process efficiency, reports T systems. E-commerce is being considered as a separate, profitable field business and intermediary actors are updating their B2B business models, while embracing aspects of social media. Besides, competitive advantages determine whether a company can move forward, E-commerce is the right tool for gaining competitive advantage now-a-days in Bangladesh. Some restrict the definition of ecommerce only to internet rather telecommunication and telecommunication based tools are also involved in ecommerce activities. In Bangladesh perspective, the broader definition is accepted to all. Like traditional commerce, e-commerce does not involved only in buying and selling of goods and services rather includes intercompany and inter-company functions like negotiations and transactions, manufacturing and marketing etc. using email, Electronic Data Interchange (EDI), fax, file transfer, video conferencing etc. depending on the involvement with electronic means, a company can be either a complete or partial e-commerce user. Much debate surrounds the blooming e-commerce industry in Bangladesh, with different views on whether the proliferation and growth of e-commerce companies and the valuation that some of them have generated is merely a bubble or just the tip of the iceberg. Right now more than 6.5 million people are using Internet in the country with the help of around 200 private registered Internet Service Providers (ISP) and dial-up services and the cost of using Internet is low. The increasing number of user of Internet creates more opportunity of ecommerce in the recent years. Around 100 million people use mobile services and 15 or 20 percent people take mobile banking services. According to data of Bangladesh Bank, about 1million mobile users take the mobile banking services and roughly over 100 core transactions are made through the mobile banking every month. In Bangladesh have more than 2500 e-commerce websites and 1 million digital buyer overall and 50% of them are from Asia market. It is clear that e-commerce industry is growing at a rapid pace in Bangladesh. Major retailers are now opening their own websites which complement their traditional bricks-and-mortar outlets. Some retailers operate solely over the Internet, especially in F-commerce (Face book commerce). Online retailers often sell products and services at a significant discount to those offered by traditional outlets. Buying online is convenient. Consumers can make their purchases from the comfort of their own homes and have them delivered to their doors. In the near future the boundaries between conventional and electronic commerce will become increasingly blurred as more and more businesses move sections of their operations onto Internet.

The tremendous growth of the Internet has created opportunities for consumers and firms to participate in an online global marketplace. The Internet has provided a rare opportunity especially for small to medium sized enterprises (SMEs). It moves organizations beyond the physical constraints of their traditional distribution channels and creates a worldwide virtual community in which SMEs can compete with large enterprises. A Web site gives direct contact between the organization and the consumer. The rapid developments of online computing technology, some especially targeted at SMEs, make it inevitable for businesses not to seriously consider the Internet as an alternative distribution channel to avoid losing competitive advantage. Since 1993, the Internet has been used to support conventional sales and marketing activities; it matches buyers and sellers in a more cost-effective manner compared with traditional advertising and marketing. While transactions are taking place on the Internet, the current level of commerce is small relative to overall commerce in the United

States. The phenomenal growth of the Internet community has begun to alter the way buyers and sellers exchange information and the structure of distribution. It breaks through the physical barriers traditionally placed on commerce and moves firms to a new commercial marketplace. In addition, the opportunity for buyers to examine or test the product or service and interact with the seller to receive additional information or support can be provided through the online service.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this research is to provide an inside scenario about the internet marketing. Particularly the main objective of this study is to examine the extent of online marketing usually using by the click and mortar business in Bangladesh. The specific objectives of this study are to find out the relationship between future purchases decisions of online customers to prior purchase experience. Another aim is to measure the impact of product quality, price, availability, distribution system, promotional programs on the online customers future purchase decision. Identify the relationship of social benefit with customers future purchase is another main objective of the study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature on web theory is scant because it is a relatively a new area and the technologists at the forefront of Web design are typically not sufficiently academically inclined to formulate the relevant theories (Day, 1997). While previous research has examined Internet usage (Teo, Lim, & Lai, 1999), commercial websites (Gonzalez and Palacios, 2004), website design (Kim, Shaw, & Schneider, 2003), website effectiveness from the consumers' perspective (Bell & Tang, 1998), pricing paid placements on search engine (Sen et. al., 2008), and bidding (Bernard and Simone, 2011). SEM is an internet marketing model aiming at promoting the ranking of websites in the search engine's search results page which can make a web site introduce into more web users and website traffic [iProspect 2008]. Li-Hsing HO et. al., (2011) explained about exploration of SEO technology applied in internet marketing, Kesharwani and Tiwari (2011) studied the importance of website quality towards the success or failure of any e-vendor. Khan and Mahapatra (2009) studied that the quality of internet banking (i-banking) services in India from customer's perspective. Malhotra and Singh (2007) carried out a research to find the i-banking adoption by the banks in India. Thus, it is high time that India should act fast and decisively in order to use the growing electronic trade to our advantage. A very common discussion in the e-marketing literature is that disintermediation will be widespread and electronic markets will automatically reduce the need for brokers (Gallaughar, 1999; Choudhury et al., 1998). It is possible to argue that the Web market can really fulfill most of the four specific missions of retailers: bringing the right product, at the right place, at the right price, and at the right time (Christensen and Tedlow, 2000) with the time function remaining as an exception for physical offerings. With this point of view, the number and functions of intermediaries may be expected to decrease substantially in this revolutionary medium.

So far it is possible to identify, a large number of research studies on the subject of online marketing has been done throughout the world. But it is difficult to find out papers that only highlight online marketing practices in Bangladesh. For having a close idea about online marketing and its supportive activates it could be helpful to go through different studies of foreign and domestic articles and research papers. This study is an attempt to organize and

summarize the literature about Internet marketing particularly online marketing and enlighten the research routes that will contribute to the advancement of the discipline.

HYPOYHESIS

1. H1: Prior purchase experience have relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
2. H2: Product quality have relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
3. H3: Perceived social benefits have relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
4. H4: Attractive promotional efforts have relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
5. H5: Efficient distribution channel have relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
6. H6: Awareness about online shopping does not have any relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
7. H7: Online product availability have relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors
8. H8: Price has relationship with customers' future purchase intention from online vendors

METHODOLOGY

Nature of the study

Both qualitative and quantitative approach was used in this study. The study was analytical and conceptual in nature based on both the primary and the secondary data. The research is conclusive in the form of descriptive design.

Sample size and Sampling method

The population of the study was the general people of northern region of Bangladesh. 150 respondents were purposively selected for this study. 50 respondents from Dinajpur city, the other 50 respondents were selected from Rangpur city rest 50 respondents are from Thakurgoan, Panchagadh, Gaibandha by using convenience sampling method. Data are collected from the respondent as per convenience and co-operative with them.

Sources of data

Primary data have been used in the present study for statistical. Primary data have been obtained from Dinajpur, Rangpur, Thakurgoan, Panchagadh, Gaibandha city through a well-designed questionnaire. Secondary data has been collected through several sources such as online directory, journals, reports, and media publications and various periodicals, internet search engine, related dissertation, related books and newspapers.

Tools for data collection

For the purpose of collecting data , Non Comparative scaling in the form of itemized rating scaling technique was used through Dichotomous scale which is ranged by 1 and 2 where 1=Yes,2=No.

Data Analysis Techniques

The primary and secondary data were analyzed through the statistical methods. SPSS was used for analyzing the data collected. Some analytical techniques like Frequency Distribution of demographic profile, Frequency Distribution and Regression analysis of the answers given by the respondents as "Yes" or "No" data. This study will cover a number of randomly chosen 150 people of Dinajpur ,Rangpur Thakurgoan, Panchagadh, Gaibandha city.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Demographic information of respondents

The table, demographic profile exhibits the age, occupation, education, income level and gender of the respondents classified in different sub-sections.

Description		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	96	64%
	Female	54	36%
Age (In years)	15-20	50	33.3%
	21-30	27	18%
	31-40	28	18.7%
	Above 40	45	30%
Occupation	Student	71	47.3%
	Businessman	18	12%
	Service holder	33	22%
	Housewife	28	18.7%
Education	SSC	48	32%
	HSC	40	26.7%
	Honors	26	17.3%
	Masters	36	24%
Level of income (Tk.)	Below 10000	76	50.7%
	10001-20000	26	17.3%
	20001-30000	19	12.7%
	Above 30000	29	19.3%

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1. Of the surveys analyzed, 96 respondents (64%) were males and 54 (36%) were females. Majority of the respondents were aged between 15-20 was 50 (33.3%) and respondents aged above 40 is 45 (30%). Most of the respondents were students (47.1%). Comparing to education level 58.7% is HSC passed. As most of the respondents were students so the lowest earner is 76 (50.7%).

Number of people who are informed about Internet Shopping

Informed about online shopping	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	120	80%
No	30	20%

Table-2: Number of people who are informed about Internet Shopping

The above table shows that among 150 respondents, 80 percent respondents have heard about online shopping. Although one fifth (20%) of them don't know that they can buy product by using internet.

Number of people who purchased product through internet

Purchased product via online	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	46	30.7%
No	104	69.3%

Table-3: Number of people who purchased product through internet

Data in table 3 shows that only 30.7% respondent have used internet to purchase product. Although 80 percent respondents heard about internet marketing, but 69.3% of them don't ever use internet to buy any product.

Products availability of in online shop

Products are available in online	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	96	64%
No	54	36%

Table-4: Products availability of online shop

From the above table, it is shown that 64 percent respondents said that they found the products that they need are available in online shop. But 36 percent respondents said that products are not available in online shop.

Products quality of online shop

Products are qualityful of online shop	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	93	62%
No	57	38%

Table-5: Products quality of online shop

From the above table, it is shown that 62 percent respondents said that the products which are available in online are good in terms of quality, but 38 percent respondents don't think that they have purchased good quality product from online shop.

Price affordability of the online products

Price is convenient	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	84	56%
No	66	44%

Table-6: Price affordability of the online products

During the research, it is found that 56 percent respondents are happy with the price of the online products set by the company. But 44 percent said that the price is high of the online products comparing with the physical market.

Effectiveness of the delivery channel

Delivery channel is effective	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	84	56%
No	66	44%

Table-7: Effectiveness of the delivery channel

From the above table, it is shown that 56 percent respondents said that the channel used by the companies to deliver the products is quite effective. And 44 percent said the delivery channel is not good or effective to serve the customers.

Effectiveness of promotional activities of online products

Promotional activities are attractive	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	102	68%
No	48	32%

Table-8: Effectiveness of promotional activities of online products

From the above table, it is shown that 68 percent respondents said that the promotional activities like advertisements, digital marketing, and campaigns are effective enough to attract the people. But 32 percent of the respondents said that the promotional activities are not effective to attract the target customer.

Societal benefit of online marketing

Societal benefit	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	114	76%
No	36	24%

Table-9: Societal benefit of online marketing

From the above table, it is shown that 76 percent respondents said that internet marketing is beneficial to society, and they can get different facilities through it. But 24 percent were disagreed with the statement.

Purchase of product in future over internet

Future purchase	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	131	80.7%
No	29	19.3%

Table-10: Purchase of product in future over internet

From the above table, it is shown that 80.7 percent respondents said that they are interested in purchasing of products through online in future. But 19.3 percent are not yet interested in purchasing products through online.

Regression Analysis Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	Change Statistics			
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2
1	.980 ^a	.960	.957	.08285	.960	419.475	8	141

a. Predictors: (Constant), Price_is_convenient, Purchased_product_over_internet, Delivery_channel_is_effective, Products_are_qualityful, Product_are_available_in_online, Promotional_activities_are_attractive, Online_marketing_has_social_benefit, Informed_about_internet_shopping
As shown in the model summary, there is a strong and positive correlation ($R = .985$) between the dependent variable (future purchase intention from online vendors) and the identified independent variables included in this study. R square turned out to be .970 which indicates that 97% variance in online purchase intention can be explained by the independent variables (price, prior purchase, effective delivery, quality products, product availability, and attractiveness of the promotion, perceived social benefit, and awareness about online shopping)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.032	8	2.879	419.475	.000 ^b
	Residual	.968	141	.007		
	Total	24.000	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase_in_future

b. Predictors: (Constant), Price_is_convenient, Purchased_product_over_internet, Delivery_channel_is_effective, Products_are_qualityful, Product_are_available_in_online, Promotional_activities_are_attractive, Online_marketing_has_social_benefit, Informed_about_internet_shopping

The following ANOVA table suggests that the model fits well to the data. Here, the null hypothesis of regression (R square in the population is zero) is rejected because p value is less than .05. It shows that some of the partial regression coefficients will have some impact on dependent variables. To investigate which coefficients are statistically significant, the research relied upon the coefficient table.

From the coefficient table, the researcher tested the null hypotheses formulated for this study. The table shows that quality products, attractive promotional activities, efficient distribution channel, awareness about online marketing and product availability positively and significantly ($p < .05$) influence customers' future purchase intentions from online vendors. So the H2, H4, H5, H6, H7 was supported. So, the researcher can conclude that with greater product quality, more attractive promotional efforts, more efficient distribution channel, higher level of awareness about online shopping, and increased availability of online merchandises, customers' intention to purchase from online marketers will increase if other variables are held constant.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.032	.033		.963	.337
Informed_about_internet_shopping	.968	.051	.980	18.795	.000
Purchased_product_over_internet	-5.391E-16	.016	.000	.000	1.000
Products_are_qualityful	-6.999E-15	.019	.000	.000	1.000
Delivery_channel_is_effective	-4.309E-15	.018	.000	.000	1.000
Promotional_activities_are_attractive	-1.458E-14	.026	.000	.000	1.000
Online_marketing_has_social_benefit	-1.813E-14	.036	.000	.000	1.000
Product_are_available_in_online	7.603E-16	.020	.000	.000	1.000
Price_is_convenient	1.228E-16	.018	.000	.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase_in_future

However, the results obtained from this could not support the H1, H3 and H8. This indicates that according to this study, prior online purchase experience, perceived social benefits and price in online shopping do not significantly contribute to future purchase intention of the customer. Although, this study did not find price to be a significant predictor of purchase intention, many prior research and theory confirms that price plays a significant role in future purchase intention.

RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATION

RESULTS

The regression analysis demonstrated that H2, H4, H5, H6, H7 were accepted, which means quality products attract more customer to make purchase. Attractive promotional activities had also impact on the future purchase decision of the customers. Efficient distribution channel is another indicator of future purchase intention. Awareness about online marketing and product availability negatively and significantly ($p < .05$) influenced customers' future purchase intentions from online vendors.

Again H1, H3 and H8 could not be accepted. Thus it was clear that prior online purchase experience had impact on the intention of future purchase of online customers. Perceived social benefits had also influence on the future purchase of the customers. Last but not the least, price of the product in online shopping significantly contributed to future purchase intention of the online customer.

RECOMMENDATION

Day by day the number of internet users is increasing. So it is mandatory to send message to all new and existing internet users that you can buy any product by using internet at your home. In rural areas people are not introduced with internet shopping, so it should be another concern for the marketer to inform and make them familiar with internet marketing. As people want everything at a single place, so marketers need to keep product variety in their online shop. All kinds of products should be available in internet for all ages' people and gender. To satisfy your customer need to provide qualityful products continuously. So every marketer of online business keep in mind that if they want stay on competition and earn profit, need to make sure of sufficient supply of qualityful products. In our country, large number of people belongs to middle-class family. So they are very price sensitive. In case of online business marketers should set the price of any product considering the affordability of the customers with handsome profit. Another important thing is to develop a simpler and easier system to deliver the product to customers home. Customers should not be disturbed or annoyed about the delivery of product.

Mass promotional activities should be undertaken (advertising, sales promotion, campaign, greeting SMS etc.) by the marketers to make their online products sold at once. Again it is the most important matter, that people should be understood about the benefits of internet shopping and internet marketing. Undertake various social campaign, online business fair, create awareness about internet marketing will be helpful to build a positive image in the mind of customers. Our research result shows that 80.7 percent of the respondents will purchase product in future via internet. Make the percentage towards 100 percent by building their awareness positively towards internet marketing.

CONCLUSION

As online marketing is a new concept in Bangladesh, many marketers still don't realize its importance and application. Some business organizations that have international business operations are exercising online marketing partially. Many business firms in Bangladesh those are high tax payers even don't have a web site. The businesses that only serve the domestic market have limited online marketing endeavor. Lack of customers' accessibility over Internet is the major setback of growing online marketing. Some brick and mortar companies changing themselves as click and mortar companies to enjoy competitive advantage. Without some auction companies and job sites it is difficult to find out pure click only companies in Bangladesh. It is not possible always to apply real world marketing practices to online marketing. Online marketing tends to be an entirely different challenge. Strategic online marketing is necessary to success on web. In fact, most of the businesses people who are on the Internet say that they use it mainly for gathering information in Bangladesh. High speed Internet accessibility is necessary to boost the online marketing practice throughout the country. This study basically measure extent of practicing online marketing of different type of business firms in Bangladesh presently. We have examined the Internet users' demands and needs online, and found that they only to a small degree ask for involvement. There are explicit demands for less advertising and simple and well structured websites, but when it comes to dialogue, and participation only a smaller part of our population asked for direct involvement. Login and personalization are however in high demand, a relatively new tool, login have appeared on more and more sites, developed from extranets (dealer logins) to consumer login to remember setup, addresses and other

information the consumer need to type each time a purchase is made. This leads us to conclude that over time the demand for further involvement will grow.

One of the most important features the internet provides is communication, communication between themselves and their customers. Companies has for a long time been using the internet as advertising tools to promote their product. In other words, it has been a one-way communication. Chat and forums is one of the possibilities the internet provides. The focus has to take a turn in the consumer's direction. So instead of one-way communication it should be two-way communication. Consumers want to able to identify themselves in the sites and product. This would be achieved through chatrooms and forums. Instead of being a visitor they would rather be participants on the sites. Conceivably more like Blogs and newsgroup provides. What we also found out, was that the entrance to a site has to be simple and direct. A concern that we were faced with, was the fact that only few companies has a list of contact persons for direct contact. Also, with larger companies a receptionist is available; why not make his/her presence available on the internet via the company website. A simple process that would start the dialogue with the visitor, perhaps reveal areas where the website are failing to meet the needs of the visitor. It would moreover be an indication that the companies involved the consumer's participants in the process.

The data collection is reliable in terms of gender or age among this 150 participants from the cities. There are some limitations that help to conduct future research in a wider scope which will produce more accurate and unbiased information. In every research work there are some limitations and this research is no exception. The study is 'micro' in nature, and its survey findings and observations cannot be generalized and may be subjected to change from time to time and place to place. When the data were input in SPSS software for future processing no data were missing. All the respondents' feedback were added carefully.

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